

EFFECT OF MACROECONOMIC RISKS ON NIGERIAN MANUFACTURING SECTOR USING ANNUAL DATA FROM 1986 - 2023

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Abstract: This study investigated the effect of macroeconomic risks on the Nigerian manufacturing sector using annual data from 1986 to 2023. The specific objectives of the study were to: examine the effect of inflation risk on the Nigerian manufacturing sector; evaluate the effect of exchange rate risk on the Nigerian manufacturing sector; ascertain the effect of interest rate risk on the Nigerian manufacturing sector; investigate the effect of unemployment rate risk on the Nigerian manufacturing sector. The study was a secondary type that adopted an ex-post facto research design. The Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) method was adopted using a multiple regression model of data analysis. It was discovered that exchange rate and interest rate risks had a significant effect on the Nigerian manufacturing sector. While inflation rate risk and unemployment rate risks had no significant effect on the Nigerian manufacturing sector. It was concluded that the selected macroeconomic variables jointly had a significant effect on the Nigerian manufacturing sectors. It was recommended that the government should come up with policies that will enhance price control, control of money supply, and increase productivity to stem the tide of inflation, interest rate, and exchange rate risks in Nigeria. The government should also create more job opportunities to reduce the rate of unemployment in Nigeria.

Keywords: Inflation rate risk, Exchange rate risk, Interest rate risk, unemployment rate risk, manufacturing sector.

1.1 Introduction

The manufacturing sector has been empirically confirmed to play a positive role in the economic development of both developed and developing economies [Tizhe *et al.*, 2022; Ogundipe, 2022; Okedele, 2023; Ogar *et al.*, 2024; Udo *et al.*, 2024; and Mazeli *et al.*, 2024]. However, like in many Sub-Saharan African countries, Nigeria's manufacturing sector growth remains very low when compared with other parts of the world (Mazeli *et al.*, 2024). The manufacturing sector's percentage of GDP continues to fluctuate, as it was 12.8%, 14.8% and 13.49% in the years 2020, 2021, and 2022, respectively. In the fourth quarter of 2023, it was 16.04%, which was higher than the figure recorded in the corresponding period of 2022 at 13.49% and lower than the third quarter of 2023 at 16.18% (CBN, 2023). The sector is dominated by the production of cement and building materials, food and beverages, tobacco, chemicals and fertilizers, wood, and textiles. Out of all only 3 subsectors (food & beverage, cement, and textile) account for 77% of manufacturing output generating the greatest value. Also, breweries and flour mills contribute well in the manufacturing sector. Manufacturing sector growth is influenced by both internal and

external economic risks. Whereas internal economic risks focus on a manufacturer's specific characteristics, the external risks concern both industry features and macroeconomic variables.

The objectives of macroeconomic policy may vary from country to country but one of the key objectives targeted by most countries is to achieve price stability, which is measured by a stable inflation rate. Inflation is assessed by the consumer price index which mirrors the yearly percentage variations in the cost to the normal consumer goods and services. Nigeria inflation rate for 2021 was 16.95%, a 3.71% increase from 2020. In 2020 it was 13.25%, a 1.85% increase from 2019; in 2019 it was 11.40%, a 0.7% decline from 2018. For 2018, it was 12.09%, a 4.43% decline from 2017. However, in January 2023, the headline inflation rate increased to 21.82% paralleled to December 2022 inflation rate which was 21.34%. Considering the trend, the January 2023 inflation rate showed an increase of 0.47%. On the other hand, on a year-by-year basis, inflation rate was 6.22% higher compared to the rate recorded in January 2022, which was 15.60%. This shows that the headline inflation rate (year-by-year basis) increased in the month of January 2023 when compared to the same month in the preceding year (NBS, 2023).

The main purpose of exchange rate policy in Nigeria is to preserve the worth of the national currency, sustain a favourable external reserves, and ensure external balance without conceding the need for internal balance and the general aim of macroeconomic stability. The exchange rate targeting and direct monetary targeting frameworks involved administrative determination of monetary policy variables. Nigeria has implemented various exchange rate regimes over time. For instance, According to Essien *et al.*, (2017), several exchange rate policies have been applied in Nigeria, ranging from a fixed exchange rate era, prior to 1985 to different practices of floating systems, due to the liberalization of the foreign exchange market in 1986. Towards the end of 1985, the government allowed the exchange rate to be determined by market forces in consonance with the tenets of the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP). Nigeria's exchange rate regime since SAP could be strictly referred to as a managed float system. (Samodet *et al.*, 2021).

Interest rate in Nigeria has been stable over the years when compared with inflation rate and exchange rate within the same period. The minimum discount rate (MDR) was initially used as a bench mark for interest rate. It was later change to the monetary policy rate (MPR) in 2006. Interest rates were set at relatively low levels primarily to encourage investment and growth. Interest rates and monetary aggregates were monetary policy aims in Nigeria (Ologunde *et al.*, 2006). The CBN raised its standard interest rate by another 50 bps to 18.5% in a decision announced on May 24th 2023, as widely expected. The headline inflation rate in Nigeria accelerated for the 5th month to 22.22% in April 2023, it's highest in almost two decades, from 22.04% in the prior month. Meanwhile, recent data showed Nigeria's economic growth decelerated to 2.31% year-on-year in the first three months of 2023, partly attributed to the adverse impacts of the cash crunch experienced throughout the quarter. The monetary authorities use direct monetary policy measures to impact items on commercial banks' balance sheets. In such a system, monetary authorities determine interest rates and credit allocations in accordance with the government's economic plan (Gimba *et al.*, 2020). The perceived instability of interest rate in Nigeria had made it difficult for investors to borrow funds (Obute *et al.*, 2012).

Manufacturing sector no doubt is an important sub sector of the Nigerian industrial sector and the Nigerian economy at large. There is no gain saying that Nigerian manufacturing sector is well placed for growth due to its growing population, currently estimated to be 200 million and an emerging middle class driving economic activity. However, it is vital to note that the level of performance of any country's manufacturing sector depends on the stability of certain macroeconomic environment. It was therefore in recognition of these facts that the

researcher investigated the effect of macroeconomic risk such as: inflation rate risk, interest rate risk, exchange rate risk and unemployment rate risk on insurance sector development in Nigeria from 1986 to 2023.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Manufacturing sector growth is influenced by both internal and external economic risks. Whereas internal economic risks focus on a manufacturer's specific characteristics, the external risks concern both industry features and macroeconomic variables. Therefore, one of the most important policy concerns of government and the Nigeria Central Bank is to enhance macroeconomic stability, which will translate into economic growth and development of Nigeria. Thus, in an ideal world, it is expected that the government macroeconomic strategies should ensure the attainment of optimal interest rate, exchange rate, inflation rate and money supply that will in turn translate to economic growth and development of Nigeria.

However, the reality is that, over the years, Nigerian's macroeconomic policy stance in all honesty have left much to be desired given how these policies and strategies have affected macroeconomic indicators. The speed of fluctuation and instability of these macroeconomic policy indicators have been explosive and worrisome, thereby constituting risks to business organizations. In the last four years, the Nigerian manufacturing sector's percentage of GDP continues to fluctuate, as it was 12.8%, 14.8% and 13.49% in years 2020, 2021 and 2022 respectively. In the fourth quarter of 2023 it was 16.04%, which was higher than the figure recorded in the corresponding period of 2022 at 13.49% and lower than the third quarter of 2023 at 16.18% (CBN, 2023). Business and financial analysts find it extremely difficult to carry out reliable business forecast. Inflation rate in Nigeria has gone so high and has adversely eroded the value of Naira in the last two years. As at the end of third quarter of 2024, Naira's exchange rate against USD was between N1,600 and N1,610 to \$1. More so, the costs of borrowing (interest rate) as well as unemployment rate have also gone very high. In the last four years, the Nigerian manufacturing sector's percentage of GDP continues to fluctuate, as it was 12.8%, 14.8% and 13.49% in years 2020, 2021 and 2022 respectively. In the fourth quarter of 2023 it was 16.04%, higher than the figure recorded in the corresponding period of 2022 at 13.49% and lower than the third quarter of 2023 at 16.18% (CBN, 2023).

The perceived negative effect of this trend has made many researchers to pay attention to the link between macroeconomic risks and manufacturing sector output growth in Nigeria [Okonkwo & Chigbu, 2016; Nwokoro, 2017; Abdallah, 2018; Anokwuru *et al.*, 2018; Douglas *et al.*, 2018; Onakoya, 2018; Falaye *et al.*, 2019; Odior, 2020; Adeniyi, 2021; Ogbonna, 2021; Nwafor, 2022; Ugwoke, 2022; Anochie *et al.*, 2023; Adeoye, 2024; Jamilu *et al.*, 2024; Thankgod & Gbarawae, 2023; Abegunde, 2024]. However, the outcomes of these studies have generated conflicting results which call for further research. It is therefore against this backdrop that the researcher studied the effect of macroeconomic risks on Nigerian manufacturing sector using annual data from 1986 to 2023. In specific terms, the researcher studied the effect of; inflation rate, exchange rate, interest rate and unemployment rate on Nigerian manufacturing sector growth rate.

1.3. Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study was to investigate the effect of macroeconomic risks factors on Nigerian manufacturing sector. While the specific objectives of the study were to:

- i. Examine the effect of inflation rate risk on Nigerian manufacturing sector;
- ii. Evaluate the effect of exchange rate risk on Nigerian manufacturing sector;
- iii. Ascertain the effect interest rate risk on Nigerian manufacturing sector;
- iv. Investigate the effect of unemployment rate risk on Nigerian manufacturing sector.

1.4. Research Questions

- i. What is the effect of inflation rate risk on Nigerian manufacturing sector?
- ii. What is the effect of exchange rate risk on Nigerian manufacturing sector?
- iii. What is the effect interest rate risk on Nigerian manufacturing sector?
- iv. What is the effect of unemployment rate risk on Nigerian manufacturing sector?

1.5. Statement of Hypotheses

Hypotheses of the study were stated in null form in line with the objectives of the study.

- i. **H₀₁**: inflation rate risk does not have significant effect on Nigerian manufacturing sector.
- ii. **H₀₂**: exchange rate risk does not have significant effect on Nigerian manufacturing sector.
- iii. **H₀₃**: interest rate risk does not have significant effect on Nigerian manufacturing sector.
- iv. **H₀₄**: unemployment rate risk does not have significant effect on Nigerian manufacturing sector.

1.6. Scope of the Study

i. Unit Scope: This study specifically investigated the effect of macroeconomic risks factors on Nigerian manufacturing sector.

ii. Content Scope: The dependent variable of the study was Nigerian manufacturing sector. This was proxied with total output growth rate of the Nigerian manufacturing sector. While the independent variable of the study was macroeconomic risk factors which was decomposed into four proxies- inflation rate risk, exchange rate risk, interest rate risk and unemployment rate risk.

iii. Geographical Scope: This study was carried out in Nigeria using data from the manufacturing sector of Nigeria and Nigerian macroeconomic risk factors.

iv. Time Scope: This study was carried out in the last quarter of 2024 using time series data covering the period of 1996 to 2023. The reason for this base year was as a
This time scope makes this study more current.

2.0: REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Macroeconomic Risk Factors

Macroeconomic risk factors were used as the independent variable for this study. In order to achieve the objective of this study, it was decomposed into four key macroeconomic risk factors: inflation rate risk, exchange rate risk, interest rate risk and unemployment rate risk.

2.1.2.1 Inflation Rate Risk

Inflation Risk is a key economic concept that refers to the potential reduction in the purchasing power of money over time attributable to rising prices of goods and services in a country. Inflation is an economic condition in which the prices of goods and services are rising across the board. It is a measure of how quickly the value of a currency is falling. Therefore, the inflation rate is measured as the annual rate of change in the Consumer Price Index (CPI). Inflation is an increase in the general level of prices of goods and services in an economy (Bawa and Abdullahi, 2017).

Adenekan and Nwanna (2021) express that Inflation has various definitions depending on how people see it. It is regarded as a rise in general level of prices. The tendency of rising prices and a fall in the value of money is known as inflation. Inflation can be described as a continuous rise in general price level. This phenomenon occurs when the aggregate demand in normal value is greater than the real productive capacity of the economy. It is a quantitative measure of the rate at which the average price level of a selected basket of goods and services in an

economy increases over a given period of time, often expressed as a percentage. Such inflation represents a decrease in the purchasing power of the national currency.

2.1.2.2 Exchange Rate Risk

Exchange rate risk refers to the risk that a company's operations and profitability may be affected by changes in the exchange rates between currencies. The exchange rate between two countries is defined as "the rate at which the currency of one country is exchanged for the currency of another country". The exchange rate is the price of the currency of one country in terms of another currency (Jingan, 2002).

2.1.2.3 Interest Rate Risk

Interest rate risk represents the potential for a lower return on investments if rates fall or higher debt servicing costs if rates rise. Jhingan (2002) cited in Nduma (2022) states that interest rate is the price paid to borrow or hold financial assets as an investment or to deposit money in a bank. Interest rate is the cost of borrowing money. It is the rate at which the borrower pays interest to the lender for the loan.

Interest rate is the cost of borrowing money. It is the proportion of the loan that the borrower pays to the lender. In other terms, it's the percentage of a loaned amount that the lender charges the borrower. It could be referred to as the price paid for borrowing or holding a financial asset as an investment or for putting money in a bank. In general, the level of an economy's interest rate indicates the amount of liquidity in that economy. High interest rates normally imply a liquidity constraint, whilst low interest rates suggest a liquidity surplus. Other factors that may influence interest rate fluctuations include an investment's term to maturity, the central bank's targeted interest rate level for achieving monetary policy and broad macroeconomic goals, and so on. It could be either the market or the policy rate. Market rates include banking system lending and deposit rates, as well as interbank rates, whereas the policy rate is normally set by a central bank. Interest rate fluctuation sends a signal to central banks, making it a crucial component to consider when formulating and implementing monetary policy.

2.1.2.4 Unemployment Rate Risk

Unemployment risk as used in this study refers to as the persistent increase in unemployment rate in a country. Unemployment rate is defined as "the percentage of people willing to work at the prevailing wage but unable to find employment". A high unemployment rate not only makes it harder to find a job, but it also makes it less rewarding for those who already have a job to find one, as they may have difficulty getting a raise or promotion. Low unemployment rate is an indicator of good economic performance. Therefore, employment security is always a major concern for economic policymakers (Ogunlade, 2007).

Unemployment simply calculates the number of people who are willing and qualified to work but could not find work and are actively seeking employment. Some unemployment calculations also include those individuals deemed under-employed. Under-employed individuals are those workers who have accepted part-time positions or positions for which they are grossly overqualified. High unemployment rates have obvious influence on consumer spending, but they also indicate poor job growth in both the private and public sectors (Obadan, 2010). International Labour Organization (ILO) (2009) defined unemployment as "a state of joblessness which occurs when people are without jobs and they have actively sought for work within the past four weeks". The classical economists defined unemployment as "the excess supply of labour over the demand for labour which is caused by adjustment in real wage". Unemployment can be defined as the number of people who are willing to work at the existing wage rate but do not find any. According to Keynes, full employment is the absence of voluntary unemployment. This implies that unemployment can be voluntary and involuntary.

2.1.3.1 Manufacturing Sector

Manufacturing sector is the sector that engages in the transformation of goods, materials or substances into new products. The transformational process can be physical, chemical or mechanical. Manufacturers often have plants, mills or factories that produce goods for public consumption. Machines and equipment are typically used in the process of manufacturing. Although, in some cases, goods can be manufactured by hand. An example of this would be baked goods, handcrafted jewellery, other handicrafts and art. The manufacturing process, therefore, begins with the product design and materials specification from which the product is made. The materials are then modified through manufacturing processes to become the required part (Dabwor, 2015). A robust manufacturing sector prevents a country from overreliance on international trade, while at the same time, giving the country full use of available resources (Okon & Osesie, 2017).

Manufacturing is a value-adding procedure that converts raw materials, components, or parts into pre-designed goods, products, or merchandise that satisfies a customer’s expectations or specifications. In earlier times, the word “manufacturing” connoted that these procedures were predominately carried out by human power, thus the word contains two parts “manu” and “facturing.” Today, much of manufacturing is being completed with the use of tools and machines on much larger scales and to much higher precision. Converting these raw materials into something more useful adds value. This added value increases the price of finished products, making manufacturing a very profitable part of the business chain. Some people specialize in the skills required to manufacture goods, while others provide the funds that businesses need to purchase the tools and materials (Ogundipe, 2022).

2.1.4 Conceptual Framework

The model in figure 2.1 explained the effect of insurance service activities on economic growth from the hypothesized (Inflation rate risk, exchange rate risk, interest rate risk and unemployment rate risk were used as independent variables) while dependent Nigerian manufacturing sector output growth rate.

Figure 1: Conceptual Model of Insurance Service Activities and economic growth

2.2 Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on two theories; New Institution Theory of Risk Management and The Enterprise Risk Management Theory.

2.2.1. New Institution Theory of Risk Management

The **New Institution Theory of Risk Management** Williamson (1998). The theory focus on shift to governance processes and socio-economic institutions that should guide risk management processes. The theory offers an alternative explanation of corporate risk management behavior of firms. The theory predicts that risk management

practices may be determined by institutions or accepted practice within a market or industry. Moreover, the theory links security with specific assets purchase, which implies that risk management can be important in contracts which bind two sides without allowing diversification, such as large financing contract.

If institutional factors do play an important role in risk management. First of all, it is important for us to understand that there may be difference among sectors. Secondly, hedging may be more popular in certain periods. However, a more concrete implication of this theory, is that shareholders may be interested in attracting block ownership by reducing company risk. This theory suggest that firm risk management practices may be influenced by the ownership structure in general and industry culture.

2.2.2 Enterprise Risk Management (ERM)

Enterprise risk management (ERM) was propounded by Committee of Sponsoring Organizations (COSO) in 2004 to addresses the evolution of enterprise risk management and the need for organizations to improve their approach to managing risk to meet the demands of an evolving business environment.

Enterprise risk management (ERM) is a methodology that looks at risk management strategically from the perspective of the entire firm or organization. It is a top-down strategy that aims to identify, assess, and prepare for potential losses, dangers, hazards, and other potentials for harm that may interfere with an organization's operations and objectives and/or lead to losses.

Enterprise risk is the extent to which the outcomes from the corporate strategy of a company may differ from those specified in its corporate objectives, or the extent to which they fail to meet these objectives (using a "downside risk" measure). The strategy selected to achieve these corporate objectives embodies a certain risk profile, which arises from the various factors that might impact on the activities, processes and resources chosen to implement the strategy (COSO, 2004).

The choice of these theories was based on:

1. The New Institutional theory predicted accurately that risk management practices may be determined by institutions or accepted practice within a market or industry.
2. The understanding that modern manufacturing company or sector faces diverse set of risks and potential dangers. In the past, companies traditionally handled their risk exposures via each division managing its own business. Enterprise risk management calls for corporations to identify all the risks they face which enables a company to see the bigger picture when using ERM. Adopting this wider picture will surely enhance effective and efficient risk management in business organizations.

2.3 Empirical Review

2.3.1 Inflation Rate Risk and Manufacturing Sector Output

Onakoya (2018) examined the impact of changes in the macroeconomic factors on the output of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria from 1981 to 2015. The findings revealed no short run association among manufacturing output and each of GDP, exchange rate, broad money supply and unemployment rate. Negative relationship existed amongst inflation rate, interest rate, exchange rate, broad money supply on one hand, and manufacturing output. The inflation rate and interest rate, were statistically insignificant. However, significant and positive relationship existed between GDP of the previous year and unemployment on the one hand and manufacturing output on the

other, at 5 percent level. The post estimation tests showed presence of serial correlation but evidence of heteroscedasticity existed which, made the model inefficient, but its estimator is still unbiased.

Ogbonna (2021) examined the impact of fluctuations of macroeconomic variables such as exchange rate, lending rates and inflation rates on the manufacturing output in Nigeria. The paper used descriptive analysis to investigate the relationship between manufacturing output and macroeconomic stability in Nigeria. The findings revealed that macroeconomic instability impacted negatively on the manufacturing output. The paper therefore recommended that policies that will streamline the multiple and volatile exchange rates, interest rate and inflation control should be designed and implemented to ensure their predictability to aid planning and attract both domestic and foreign investors to the, manufacturing sector.

Ugwoke (2022) investigated the impact of inflation on the manufacturing sector output in Nigeria using time series data obtained from Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin, National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), World Bank Development Indicators (WDI) and World Economic Organization (WEO). The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bound test approach was adopted. The result revealed that inflation rate was correctly signed and thus had a negative effect on the manufacturing sector output, although this proved to be statistically insignificant. The paper recommended that government should encourage investors in local raw materials through direct incentives, and overhaul access to credit for the productive sector particularly the manufacturing sector.

Anochie (2023) examined the effect of macroeconomic variables (exchange rate, interest rate and inflation rate) on productivity of Nigeria's manufacturing sector. Three research hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The used study used secondary data collected from annual time series from 1980-2020 obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin. The ordinary least squares, co-integration and regression statistics were used to analyse the data. The study found that exchange rate and interest rate has significant effect on the productivity of Nigeria's manufacturing sector; and that inflation rate has no significant effect on the productivity of Nigeria's manufacturing sector.

Ihugba (2023) investigated the relationship between inflation and Nigerian manufacturing sector growth between 1981 and 2019, utilizing performance measures such as inflation rate, money supply, and gross domestic investment. They found that in the short and long run, inflation and manufacturing sector growth are unrelated. Changes in Nigeria's inflation rate do not explain changes in the manufacturing sector's growth. The data also suggest that inflation does not assist producers with pricing power and that a fall in money supply has resulted in a decrease in manufacturing sector growth. The paper suggests that policymakers make huge investments in infrastructures that is insufficient, such as power supply and road network.

Adeoye (2024) examined the effect of inflation rate on the performance of manufacturing and agricultural sectors. Yearly data were used from 1975 to 2020. The Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) was used to analyze the data. Based on ARDL approach, the results show that agricultural equipment and exchange rate were statistically significance to agricultural output. Foreign direct investment, and inflation rate has statistical significance on manufacturing output. It was therefore recommended that Government should always check on the increase of inflation rate and how it is affecting the performance of the manufacturing sector and agricultural sectors so as to provide necessary solution in case if any problem arises. There should be an encouragement of foreign investment into the manufacturing sector in the country.

2.3.2 Exchange Rate Risk and Manufacturing Sector Output

Oriji *et al.* (2019) estimated the impact of exchange rate (EXCH) movements on the manufacturing sector in Nigeria over the period 1981–2016. Time series data and ordinary least square (OLS) estimation technique were

employed in this study to address the specified objective. Specifically, the findings showed that EXCH, government capital expenditure (GCEXP), imports and FDI were positively related to MGDP.

Falaye *et al.* (2019) studied the impact of exchange rates on the performance of the Nigerian manufacturing sector. Johansen co-integration test, Granger causality test and Error Correction Model were used to test for long-run relationship, causal relationship, and the short and long run equilibrium relationship respectively. The empirical results of the study shows that a devaluation of the Naira has a negative impact on the performance of the Nigerian manufacturing sector as it was found that exchange rate has a negative significant relationship, long run relationship and causal relationship with the performance of the sector. It was also ascertained from the results that inflation rates (INF), and capacity utilization rates (CUR) have a positive significant relationship with the performance of the sector, while exchange rates, imports (IMP) and manufacturing foreign direct investment (MFDI) have a negative significant relationship with the performance of the Nigerian manufacturing sector.

King (2019) examined the effect of exchange rate fluctuations on the Nigerian manufacturing Sector. Multiple linear regression was adopted, employing Ordinary Least Square (OLS) techniques. From the results it was observed that exchange rate has no significant effect on manufacturing output growth in Nigeria.

Mlambo and McMillan (2020) used the panel group FMOLS and PMG approaches to examine the impact of the exchange rate on manufacturing performance in SACU states from 1995–2016 and found that exchange rate, imports and FDI have a negative relationship with manufacturing performance. Exports and inflation had a positive relationship with manufacturing performance.

Uruakpa *et al.* (2021) examined the effect of exchange rate movement and exchange rate volatility on the performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria from 1985 to 2019. They utilized ordinary least square log model, and Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedastic (GARCH) model to capture the research objectives. The results show that appreciation of Nigerian domestic currency has significant positive effect on Nigerian manufacturing performance while exchange rate volatility has significant negative effect on Nigerian manufacturing output.

2.3.3 Interest Rate Risk and Manufacturing Sector

Nwokoro (2017) analyzed the impact of foreign exchange and interest rates variations on the Nigeria's manufacturing output during the period 1983 to 2014. The study employed the Ordinary Least Square (OLS), stationarity, co-integration, together with Error Correction Modelling, to know the significance and relationship between Foreign Exchange Rate, Interest Rate, Capacity Utilization, Government Expenditure on Manufacturing Sector, Investment in Industrial production and Manufacturing Output in Nigeria within the period under review. They found out that Foreign Exchange Rate (FREX) and Interest Rates (INTR) have negative but significant relationship with manufacturing Output (MANO).

Adigun *et al.* (2022) examined the impact of interest rate on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria between 1988 and 2018. ARDL test was utilized because of different order of integration of the variables. The result showed that commercial banks total loan volume and inflation rate had positive impacts on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria during the period covered while interest rate had negative impact on manufacturing sector output of Nigeria.

Odungweru *et al.* (2022) assessed the effect of interest rate on manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria between 1981 and 2019. Time series data on manufacturing production, lending rate, savings deposit rate, exchange rate, manufacturing capacity utilization rate and commercial banks loans & advances were sourced

secondarily. They found that lending rate negatively affected manufacturing sector output while commercial banks loans and advances did not meaningfully improve manufacturing sector production.

Nwafor (2022) examined the impact of interest rate spread and exchange rate volatility on manufacturing output in Nigeria between the periods of 1981-2020. The work adopted the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method of estimation and employed Newey-West-HAC to correct heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation problems intrinsically. The result revealed that, despite being significant, a negative relationship exists between foreign direct investment and manufacturing output consequently. The findings also show that government capital expenditure is significant but negatively related to capital formation.

Thankgod and Gbarawae (2023) evaluated the effects of exchange, and interest rates on manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria. In order to determine whether there is a long-run relationship between interest rate, exchange rate, and inflation, a bound test was conducted using the Auto-regressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) model. High volatility in exchange and interest rates have a positive effect on manufacturing sector performance, as shown by the results of the Autoregressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) bound test, and the results from Arch and Garch corroborate these findings. Auto-regressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) results indicated a positive and statistically significant relationship between the exchange rate and the performance of the manufacturing sector over time at 0.05 level. However, bank size revealed a positive but non-significant relationship with manufacturing sector performance in the short-run, while the coefficient of interest rate spread and inflation rate were both negative and significantly influenced manufacturing sector performance.

Abegunde (2024) carried out a comparative analysis of interest rate and manufacturing output in West Africa using correlation analysis, Kao Cointegration, Cross Sectional Dependence Tests Panel Unit Root Test, Panel Auto-regressive Distributed Lags. The results from the findings showed that interest rate has negative and significant impact on manufacturing output in WAMZ countries. Contrariwise, it exhibits a positive impact on WAEMU countries. This shows that as interest rate is falling, manufacturing sector will be experiencing growth and thereby getting improvement in output but in WAEMU, it means that as interest rate increases, manufacturing sector will experience growth in output.

2.3.4 Unemployment Rate Risk and Manufacturing Sector Output

Clement and Hlalefang (2018) used quarterly data from 1994 to 2016 to investigate the trend of the impact of unemployment on economic growth in South Africa. The analysis used the ARDL (Autoregressive Distributed Lag) method. The results show that there was a negative relationship between unemployment rate and economic growth in both the short and long term.

Setet al. (2018) investigated the relationship between unemployment rate and economic growth in Nigeria from 1986 to 2015. The ARDL (Autoregressive distributed lag) boundary test and the economic error correction model (ECM) of the ARDL model were used for the evaluation. The results show that there is a long-run relationship between unemployment and economic growth in Nigeria. The results also show that unemployment in Nigeria increases growth during the study period.

Adeniyi (2021) examined whether the Nigerian manufacturing sector creates more jobs during economic expansions, which did not occur between 1981 and 2014. The study examined industry employment intensity of gross value-added rise during expansion using the Vector Error Correction Model. (VECM). Over the past year, manufacturing employment was inversely associated with agriculture employment. The data also show that manufacturing employment is connected with administration and social services employment throughout the past

year. Manufacturing's employment elasticity of growth compared to administration and social services was 5.26 per cent a year later.

Ogar *et al.* (2024) studied the impact of manufacturing output on employment in Nigeria. The Autoregressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) estimation technique was used to establish the long run relationship among the variables. It was revealed that long run relationship exists among the variables in the estimated model. The results of the Error Correction Mechanism (ECM) within the framework of the ARDL shows that the development of the manufacturing sector is one of the key strategies for the creation of employment opportunities in Nigeria.

3.0: METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The researcher adopted an *ex-post facto* research design in this study. This is a type of research design which aims at determining the relationship between one variable and another or the effect of one variable on another, and the variables involved are not manipulated by the researcher (Onwumere, 2020). Kerlinger (1964) defines *Ex post facto* research as: that research in which the independent variable or variables have already occurred. The choice of this research design was based on the fact that the researcher utilized existing time series data to carry out this study.

3.2 Area of the Study

This study titled effect of macroeconomic risks factors on Nigerian manufacturing sector was carried out in Nigeria. It focused on the Nigeria manufacturing sector and macroeconomic risk factors in Nigeria.

3.3. Nature and Sources of Data

Already existing statistical data were used for this study. Data were sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin for various years.

3.6 Model Specification

The study adopted empirical model of Charles and Fabian (2014) which was specified as:

$$\text{INFLR} = f(\text{SM}; \text{INT}; \text{EXR})$$

The linear equation of this model was written as:

$$\text{INFLR}_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{MSt} + \beta_2 \text{INT}_t + \beta_4 \text{EXR}_t + \epsilon_t$$

Where: INFLR = Rate of Inflation

SM = Supply of Money

INTR = Interest Rate

EXCR = Exchange Rate

β = is the constant term $\beta_1 - \beta_3$ = Parameters of the explanatory variables to be assessed.

ϵ = Error term

In order to adequately capture the broad objectives of this study, the above model was modified as follows:

The functional relation of the model was specified as:

$$\text{NMSGR} = f(\text{IFLRR}, \text{EXCRR}, \text{INFRR}, \text{UNERR}) \quad \text{. (i)}$$

While the general model was specified as follows:

$$\text{NMSGR} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{IFLRR}_{t1} + \beta_2 \text{EXCRR}_{t2} + \beta_3 \text{INFRR}_{t3} + \beta_4 \text{UNERR}_{t4} + \mu \quad \text{. (ii)}$$

Where: NMSGR = Nigerian Manufacturing Sector Growth Rate

INFRR = Inflation Rate Risk

EXCRR = Exchange Rate Risk

INTRR = Interest Rate Risk

UNERR= Unemployment Rate Risk

$\beta_0 - \beta_4$ = Constant parameters;

t = time series

μ = Error term

3.7 Description of Model Variable

3.7.1 Independent Variables

Macroeconomic risk factors were used as the independent variable for this study. In order to achieve the objective of this study, it was decomposed into four key macroeconomic risk factors: inflation rate risk, exchange rate risk, interest rate risk and unemployment rate risk.

Inflation Risk: Inflation Risk is a key economic concept that refers to the potential reduction in the purchasing power of money over time attributable to rising prices of goods and services in a country. Inflation is an economic condition in which the prices of goods and services are rising across the board. It is a measure of how quickly the value of a currency is falling. Therefore, the inflation rate is measured as the annual rate of change in the Consumer Price Index (CPI).

Exchange Rate Risk: Exchange rate risk refers to the risk that a company's operations and profitability may be affected by changes in the exchange rates between currencies. The exchange rate between two countries is defined as "the rate at which the currency of one country is exchanged for the currency of another country". The exchange rate is the price of the currency of one country in terms of another currency (Jingan, 2002).

Interest Rate Risk: interest rate risk represents the potential for a lower return on investments if rates fall or higher debt servicing costs if rates rise. Jhingan (2002) cited in Nduma (2022) states that interest rate is the price paid to borrow or hold financial assets as an investment or to deposit money in a bank. Interest rate is the cost of borrowing money. It is the rate at which the borrower pays interest to the lender for the loan.

Unemployment Rate Risk: Unemployment risk as used in this study refers to as the persistent increase in unemployment rate in a country. Unemployment rate is defined as "the percentage of people willing to work at the prevailing wage but unable to find employment". A high unemployment rate not only makes it harder to find a job, but it also makes it less rewarding for those who already have a job to find one, as they may have difficulty getting a raise or promotion. Low unemployment rate is an indicator of good economic performance. Therefore, employment security is always a major concern for economic policymakers (Ogunlade, 2007).

3.7.2 Dependent Variables

Manufacturing Sector: This was proxied with growth rate of total output of Nigerian Manufacturing Sector. It comprises of the growth rate in value of all goods manufactured in Nigerian economy.

3.8 Method of Data Analysis

The Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) method was adopted using a multiple regression model of data analysis. Data for the study were subjected to pretest before the main regression test was carried out to guard against getting spurious and misleading results, and to ensure that the outcome of this study can be used for meaningful prediction. These tests include: Unit root test, correlation test, normality test, trend analysis and descriptive tests. Stationarity test was done using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller. Hypotheses were tested at 5% level of significance and 95% confidence level. The P-value was the basis for decision making at the end of the test of each hypothesis.

4.0: DATA ANALYSIS

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics

Parameters	LEXCRR	LINFRR	LINTRR	LNMSGR_B	LUNERR
Mean	4.256413	2.648986	2.305462	2.874265	1.438964
Median	4.846014	2.559416	2.311527	2.899772	1.353255
Maximum	6.469545	4.341205	3.269189	4.211535	2.230014
Minimum	0.703098	-1.609438	0.875469	1.223775	1.121678
Std. Dev.	1.485367	0.977832	0.515443	0.591884	0.213378
Skewness	-0.730587	-1.861166	-0.917835	-0.793046	1.804926
Kurtosis	2.468674	10.86442	4.163513	4.141954	6.469383
Jarque-Bera	3.827450	119.8660	7.478786	6.047932	39.69044
Probability	0.147530	0.000000	0.023769	0.048608	0.000000
Obs	38	38	38	38	38

Source: Extracted from E-view 10 Statistic Package

Table 4.3 presents the descriptive statistics of our data set, and shows that, on the average, LEXCRR was 4.26%, LINFRR was 2.65%, LINTRR was 2.31%, LMSGR was 2.87%, and LUNERR was 1.44% and the highest value one was LEXCRR. The LINFRR, LINTRR and LMSGR peaked at 2.65%%, 2.31%% and 2.87% respectively. Estimate of the standard deviations revealed that apart from LEXCRR whose standard deviation is very close to the mean, the dataset of all other variables in the study are not highly volatile. In addition, the results shows that the data series of our response variable which is LEXCRR, LINFRR, LINTRR and LMSGR is negatively skewed apart from LUNERR positively skewed, has no excess kurtosis and follows normal distribution (J-B = 3.83, 119.8, 7.48, 6.04, 39.7, some P value showed significant and non-significant >0.05); hence, statistically different from zero.

The data series of all the variables are negatively skewed ($Sk > 0$) while that of LUNERR is positively skewed ($SK < 0$). There is excess kurtosis ($K > 3.0$) in series of all the independent variables. The rest independent variables have their kurtosis less than or not significantly above 3.0; hence, they are confirmed to follow normal distribution.

4.2.2: Trend Analysis

Source: Researcher’s Computation using E-views 10.0

Fig. 4.1: Graphical Representation of the Variables

The graphical representation shows that inflation rate risk, exchange rate risk, interest rate risk and unemployment rate risk have produced serious oscillation movement across the variables under the study. Meanwhile, none of the variables maintain consistency within and outside the model.

4.2.3 Pairwise Correlations

Table 4.2: Correlation Matrix

Covariance Analysis: Ordinary
 Date: 11/18/24 Time: 06:24
 Sample: 1986 2023
 Included observations: 38

Correlation	LOGEXCRR	LOGINFRR	LOGINTRR	LOGNMSGR_B	LOGUNERR
t-Statistic					
Probability					
LOGEXCRR	1.000000				
LOGINFRR	-0.206549	1.000000			
	-1.266605	----			
	0.2134	----			
LOGINTRR	-0.563005	0.139515	1.000000		
	-4.087375	0.845358	----		
	0.0002	0.4035	----		
LOGNMSGR_B	-0.146554	-0.005798	0.025373	1.000000	

	0.888922	-0.034786	0.152287	----	
	0.3799	0.9724	0.8798	----	
LOGUNERR	-0.351167	0.025758	0.221729	0.327603	1.000000
	-2.250318	0.154602	1.364333	2.080424	-----
	0.0306	0.8780	0.1809	0.0447	-----

Source: Researcher’s E-views 10.0 Output, 2024.

The bivariate Pearson correlation in Table 4.4 below portrays a significant connection of the predictor (or independent) variables with the dependent variable. Specifically, the result shows that some variable interact positively while some interact negatively with the variables of the study. All interactions were substantial.

4.2.4 Unit Root Test

The data series were subjected to unit root test. The outcome of the unit root test resulted in the generation of data series free from unit root as shown in table 4.3.4 below.

Table 4.3: Summary of Unit Root Test

Parameter	ADF-Stat	Probability value	Order of integration	Inference
LEXCRR	-6.06	0.0000	I(0)	Stationary
LINFRR	-4.65	0.0006	I(0)	Stationary
LINTRR	-4.16	0.0001	I(0)	Stationary
LNMSGR	-4.18	0.0001	I(0)	Stationary
LUNERR	-5.33	0.0001	I(1)	Stationary

Researcher’s E-views 10.0 Output.

Result of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and unit root test as provided in table 4.5 above shows that the time series data achieved stationarity at mixed levels: orders zero and one their levels. The unit root test result shows that Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression analysis is not fit for further statistical analysis, rather the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) estimation technique because of combination of I(0) and I(1) at the same time and there is no evidence for auto correlation test.

4.3 Test of Hypotheses

Test of hypotheses was done in this section. All the hypotheses stated earlier in chapter one of this research were tested using Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) method. In arriving at a decision, the following steps were taken:

- i) Restatement of hypotheses in null and alternate forms.
- ii) Presented of ARDL multiple regression result.
- iii) Decision

Decision Rule

Accept Ho if the P-value calculated is greater than (0.05) level of significance, otherwise rejects Ho and accept Hi.

Table 4.6 ARDL Regression Result for Test of Hypothesis One

Dependent Variable: NMSGR
 Method: ARDL
 Date: 11/21/24 Time: 17:18
 Sample (adjusted): 1986 2023
 Included observations: 38 after adjustments
 Maximum dependent lags: 5 (Automatic selection)
 Model selection method: Akaike info criterion (AIC)
 Dynamic regressors (5 lags, automatic): UNERR INTRR INFRR EXCRR
 Fixed regressors: C
 Number of models evaluated: 6480
 Selected Model: ARDL(5, 5, 3, 2, 5)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
NMSGR(-1)	-0.228070	0.125291	-1.820321	0.1062
NMSGR(-2)	0.142259	0.136260	1.044024	0.3270
NMSGR(-3)	-0.749195	0.143556	-5.218818	0.0008
NMSGR(-4)	0.232976	0.167521	1.390723	0.2018
NMSGR(-5)	-0.255979	0.120955	-2.116312	0.0672
UNERR	-1.092234	3.207700	-0.340504	0.7422
UNERR(-1)	3.361370	6.895439	0.487477	0.6390
UNERR(-2)	-2.630030	4.330891	-0.607272	0.5605
UNERR(-3)	-0.041445	2.327938	-0.017803	0.9862
UNERR(-4)	6.551584	1.756779	3.729315	0.0058
UNERR(-5)	10.60091	1.671406	6.342511	0.0002
INTRR	1.661352	0.378889	4.384801	0.0023
INTRR(-1)	-3.112605	0.363122	-8.571792	0.0000
INTRR(-2)	1.464577	0.413194	3.544527	0.0076
INTRR(-3)	-1.347511	0.373719	-3.605680	0.0069
INFRR	-0.210361	0.178611	-1.177756	0.2727
INFRR(-1)	0.083633	0.195149	0.428560	0.6795
INFRR(-2)	0.782347	0.196144	3.988632	0.0040
EXCRR	-0.150460	0.042261	-3.560280	0.0074
EXCRR(-1)	0.197201	0.080744	2.442288	0.0404
EXCRR(-2)	-0.097067	0.063583	-1.526622	0.1654
EXCRR(-3)	0.021396	0.063811	0.335301	0.7460
EXCRR(-4)	0.188748	0.064968	2.905237	0.0197
EXCRR(-5)	-0.201072	0.049187	-4.087907	0.0035
C	-23.51915	8.981834	-2.618525	0.0307

R-squared	0.989101	Mean dependent var	20.31212
Adjusted R-squared	0.956403	S.D. dependent var	15.99206
S.E. of regression	3.339125	Akaike info criterion	5.347380
Sum squared resid	89.19806	Schwarz criterion	6.481098
Log likelihood	-63.23177	Hannan-Quinn criter.	5.728842
F-statistic	30.24981	Durbin-Watson stat	2.230364
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000017		

*Note: p-values and any subsequent tests do not account for model selection

Researcher's E-views 10.0 Output.

4.3.1 Test of Hypothesis One

Step I: Restatement of the hypotheses in null and alternate form

H₀₁: Inflation rate risk does not have significant effect on Nigerian manufacturing sector.

H_{a1}: Inflation rate risk has significant effect on Nigerian manufacturing sector.

Step II Presentation of Result

Using extract from **Table 4.6** for test of hypothesis one, the regression result shows that the p-value was [0.2727] and the estimated coefficient was (-0.210361).

Step III: Decision

Based on the observed P-value result, the null hypothesis was accepted because the probability value (0.2727) was greater than 0.05 levels of significance. While the coefficient of determination which was -0.210361 indicated that a unit increase in inflation rate will cause about 21% decrease in Nigerian manufacturing sector output growth. The Durbin-Watson was estimated at 2.2. Following the rule of thumb, it indicates that the model is free from autocorrelation problem.

Based on the p-value [0.2727], it was decided that inflation rate risk does not have significant effect on Nigerian manufacturing sector. This implies that inflation rate risk does not have appreciable effect on Nigerian manufacturing sector output growth for the period studied. However, the negative coefficient implies that inflation risk if not checkmated can have unwanted effect on Nigerian manufacturing sector.

4.3.2 Test of Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Exchange rate risk does not have significant effect on Nigerian manufacturing sector.

H_{a2}: Exchange rate risk has significant effect on Nigerian manufacturing sector.

Step II Presentation of Result

Using extract from **Table 4.6** for test of hypothesis two, the regression result shows that the p-value was [0.0074] and the estimated coefficient was (-0.150460).

Step III: Decision

Based on the observed P-value result, the null hypothesis was rejected because the probability value (0.0074) was less than 0.05 levels of significance. While the coefficient of determination which was (-0.150460) indicated that a unit increase in exchange rate will cause about 15% decrease in Nigerian manufacturing sector output growth. The Durbin-Watson estimate of 2.2, following the rule of thumb indicates that the model is free from autocorrelation problem.

Based on the p-value [0.0074], it was decided that exchange rate risk have significant effect on Nigerian manufacturing sector. This implies that exchange rate risk is one of the factors that have caused appreciable negative effect on Nigerian manufacturing sector output growth for the period studied.

4.3.3 Test of Hypothesis Three

H₀₃: Interest rate risk does not have significant effect on Nigerian manufacturing sector.

H_{a3}: Interest rate risk has significant effect on Nigerian manufacturing sector.

Step II Presentation of Result

Using extract from Table 4.6 for test of hypothesis three, the regression result shows that the p-value was [0.0023] and the estimated coefficient was (0.661352).

Step III: Decision

Based on the observed P-value result, the null hypothesis was rejected because the probability value (0.0023) was less than 0.05 levels of significance. The coefficient of determination which was (0.661352) indicated that a unit increase in interest rate will cause about 66% change in Nigerian manufacturing sector output growth. While the Durbin-Watson estimate of 2.2, following the rule of thumb indicated that the model was free from autocorrelation problem.

Based on the p-value [0.0023], it was decided that interest rate risk have significant effect on Nigerian manufacturing sector. This implies that interest rate risk is one of the factors that have caused appreciable positive effect on Nigerian manufacturing sector output growth for the period studied.

4.3.4 Test of Hypothesis Four

Step I: Restatement of the hypotheses in null and alternate form

H₀₄: Unemployment rate risk does not have significant effect on Nigerian manufacturing sector.

H_{a4}: Unemployment rate risk has significant effect on Nigerian manufacturing sector.

Step II: Presentation of Result

Using extract from Table 4.6 for test of hypothesis four, the regression result shows that the p-value was [0.7422] and the estimated coefficient was (-1.092234).

Step III: Decision

Based on the observed P-value result, the null hypothesis was accepted because the probability value (0.7422) was greater than 0.05 levels of significance. While the coefficient of determination which was -0.092234 indicated that a unit increase in unemployment rate will cause about 9% decrease in Nigerian manufacturing sector output growth. The Durbin-Watson was estimated of (2.2) following the rule of thumb, indicates that the model was free from autocorrelation problem.

Based on the p-value [0.7422], it was decided that unemployment rate risk does not have significant effect on Nigerian manufacturing sector. This implies that unemployment rate risk does not have appreciable effect on Nigerian manufacturing sector output growth for the period studied. However, the negative coefficient implies that unemployment risk if not checkmated can wield unwanted effect on Nigerian manufacturing sector.

4.5 Discussion of Findings

4.5.1: Discussion of result on Effect of Inflation Rate Risk on Nigeria Manufacturing Sector

The result of hypothesis one showed that inflation rate risk does not have significant effect on Nigerian manufacturing sector. This result is not in total agreement with the study of Okoro and Amechi (2024) who studied the impact of inflation and stagflation on economic growth in Nigeria and found that inflation and stagflation had significant negative impact on economic growth in Nigeria.

4.5.2: Discussion of result on Effect of Exchange Rate Risk on Nigeria Manufacturing Sector

The result of hypothesis two shows that exchange rate risk had negative and significant effect on Nigerian manufacturing sector. This result in terms of magnitude is in agreement with the study of Sekyen *et al.* (2024) who conducted a study on exchange rate volatility and manufacturing sector exports in Nigeria and found that exchange rate volatility had positive and statistically significant impact on manufacturing sector export in Nigeria in the long run.

4.5.3: Discussion of result on Effect of Interest Rate Risk on Nigeria Manufacturing Sector

The result of hypothesis three shows that interest rate risk had positive and significant effect on Nigerian manufacturing sector with necessary statistical evidence stated above. This result is in agreement with that of Pam *et al.* (2021) who studied the effects of interest rates on performance of manufacturing sector in Nigeria. Their cointegration test showed a relationship between manufacturing sector output and interest rates and no cointegration of interest rates with manufacturing capacity utilization and value added.

4.5.2: Discussion of result on Effect of unemployment Rate Risk on Nigeria Manufacturing Sector. The result of hypothesis four shows that unemployment rate risk had negative and non-significant effect on Nigerian manufacturing sector. This result is in agreement with study of Abdulkareem (2024) who studied the effect of unemployment on output growth in Nigeria and found that unemployment rate had a negative effect on economic growth as well as output growth in each of three sectors (viz: agricultural, industrial and services).

5.0 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of Findings

Based on the test of hypotheses carried out in chapter four, it was discovered that:

- i. Inflation rate risk had no significant effect on Nigerian manufacturing sector. Based on P-value of $0.2727 > 0.05$.
- ii. Exchange rate risk had significant effect on Nigerian manufacturing sector. Based on P-value of $0.0074 < 0.05$.
- iii. Interest rate risk had significant effect on Nigerian manufacturing sector. Based on P-value of $0.0023 < 0.05$.
- iv. Unemployment rate risk had no significant effect on Nigerian manufacturing sector. Based on P-value of $0.7422 > 0.05$.

5.2 Conclusion

Based on these findings, it was concluded the risks of the selected macroeconomic variable jointly have significant effect on Nigerian manufacturing sectors. This conclusion was established from the fact that the P-value (0.000017) of F-statistic which showed significant statistical association with Nigerian manufacturing sector output growth rate.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government should come up with policies that will reduce the present high rate of inflation in Nigeria such as: price control measures, control of money supply and increase in productivity to ensure that there is just enough money in circulation to influence real economic growth that will help reduce inflation in Nigeria.
2. There is need for Central Bank of Nigeria to stem the tide of declining fortune of Naira in the forex market in order to facilitate insurance development in Nigeria and other businesses in the economy. This can be achieved through monetary policy objectives directed at curtailing the free fall of naira.
3. There is need for monetary authorities to come up with monetary policy rate (MPR) that will enhance Nigerian manufacturing sector growth. This can be achieved by reducing the current MPR which was raised to 18.75% in July 2023.
4. Government should create more job opportunities to reduce the rate of unemployment in Nigeria.

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